

DIRECTIONS D3.1:

Report with summary of existing DC protection options for electrical energy hubs

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Executive Summary

Introduction

This report presents the first part of the outcomes of DIRECTIONS Work Package 3 on *Methodologies for designing protection of energy hubs*. The aim of this document is to provide an overview of DC protection options for electrical energy hubs, by summarizing the findings from the fundamental research conducted mainly in *T3.1 - Shortlisting and initial screening of protection design for energy hubs*. This task focused on creating an understanding of the challenges and opportunities related to HVDC protection in electrical energy hubs, and using this to provide an initial overview of possible protection system implementations in future systems.

Key Contributions

Identification of DC Protection Challenges for Electrical Energy Hubs

Specific challenges for Electrical Energy Hubs (EEH) are identified based on a clear proposed definition and key functionalities of the grid concept studied in the DIRECTIONS project. These identified functionalities, challenges and definition provide a clear framework for the necessary studies, not only for protection but also for planning and control. Therefore, they serve as a basis for the fundamental research conducted in this project, providing a clear context for the developed methods and the conducted studies. Moreover, the broad overview of technical challenges, which are not all considered in full in this project, contributes to the identification of future research needs around EEHs, which can be clearly positioned and linked to existing research thanks to the provided unambiguous definition.

Shortlisting Method for DC Protection Configurations

This deliverable provides a methodology for shortlisting protection system configurations for HVDC switching stations in multiterminal HVDC grids and electrical energy hubs (or *energy islands*). This novel approach focuses on the configuration of protection equipment and the arrangement of lines and converters in various protection zones, instead of expert decisions on protection strategies based on numerous simulations. A graph-based approach that allows high-level evaluation of possible DC fault impacts is presented. This method can evaluate many possible protection configurations allowing the selection of less obvious choices, as experts cannot consider all possible configurations, especially for increasing switching station sizes. A filtering process reduces the number of possible configurations based on multiple protection performance metrics which are evaluated for different power flow scenarios. The results for these performance metrics are compared for configurations with different numbers of HVDC circuit breakers to assess the benefit of increasing the amount of protection equipment in different network topologies. It is also shown that, through continued filtering using additional performance metrics or fault scenarios, the number of possible breaker, cable and converter configurations can be further reduced, leading to a protection design that is well suited for many operational scenarios. The results provide insights on the required number of HVDC circuit breakers to limit fault impacts to a given value. Moreover, observed trends in the results could, in future studies, contribute to new design principles and priorities, allowing system developers to more effectively design HVDC protection systems for different operational scenarios and possible investment levels.

The presented method serves as an applicable tool for the screening of conceptual DC protection system designs for electrical energy hubs and has been applied in the industrial case studies performed in WP6 of this project. Moreover, it has been further developed into a *Mixed-Integer Linear Programming* optimization method for the general protection system design methodology, presented in D3.3.

Techno-Economic Evaluation of Alternative DC Protection Concept: Preventive Decoupling

To complete the screening of DC protection options for electrical energy hubs, the preventive decoupling concept is considered, in this report, as a potential alternative to selective DC protection using DCCBs. First, it is explained how this concept could be used to perform the key protection system function of limiting the loss-of-infeed caused by DC faults to below the di-

mensioning incident. Second, this concept is evaluated and compared to a DCCB-based protection system based on the operational costs. These costs are quantified with respect to the total generation costs of the power system and are caused by the reduction of operational flexibility in the preventive decoupling scenario. This comparison is performed in an Optimal Power Flow (OPF) framework for two realistic EEH case studies considering different future grid scenarios, to provide a thorough (methodology for) techno-economic analysis of the considered DC protection options.

Chapter 1

Introduction and Motivation

DC protection has been a key obstacle to the development of multiterminal HVDC grids for many years [1]. However, past research projects have recently provided significant insights into this subject, leading to the definition of conceptual, system-level protection strategies [2, 3], the development and testing of commercially available HVDC circuit breakers (DCCB) [4–6], and various methods for the conceptual and detailed design of DC protection systems [7–10]. As a result, although no selective HVDC protection systems are in operation in Europe today, it is expected that they will be considered in multiterminal HVDC grid projects in the future.

Recently, proposals for HVDC grid development have often included the concept of *DC hubs*, *energy hubs*, or *energy islands* [11–14]. This report investigates the DC protection options for these *electrical energy hub*-based systems, since they, in some cases, vary significantly from the examples typically considered in HVDC protection studies. Therefore, it is first aimed in Chapter 2 to identify the key protection-related challenges for these systems. A definition that can help identify similar cases is proposed and the key functionalities of electrical energy hubs (EEH) are summarized. Subsequently, the opportunities for protection system design in EEHs are explored. Chapter 3 considers the placement of DCCBs and the configuration of protection zones, which has typically been limited to the selection of a *protection strategy*. However, a novel method, developed specifically for EEHs, is proposed, allowing the efficient identification of effective protection system configurations, beyond the typically identified pre-defined protection strategies. This method forms the basis for the system-level conceptual design part of the overall protection system design methodology for EEHs, proposed in Deliverable 3.3. Lastly, this report considers a novel, alternative DC protection concept in Chapter 4 and evaluates it practically.

The content in this deliverable is based on the following papers:

- G. Bastianel, J. Kircheis, M. Van Deyck, D. Lee, G. Chaffey, M. Vanin, H. Ergun, J. Beerten and D. Van Hertem, "Review, definition and challenges of electrical energy hubs," in: *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, vol. 226, 2026, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2025.116258>. [15]
- M. Van Deyck, G. Chaffey and D. Van Hertem, "Shortlisting Protection Configurations for HVDC Grids and Electrical Energy Hubs," arXiv:2505.05886. [16]
- M. Van Deyck, G. Bastianel, G. Chaffey, H. Ergun and D. Van Hertem, "Techno-Economic Comparison of Preventive DC-Side Decoupling and DC Circuit Breakers in Multiterminal Offshore HVDC Grids," in: *IET Conference Proceedings CP918*, 2025, <https://doi.org/10.1049/icp.2025.1196>. [17]

Chapter 2

Definition of Electrical Energy Hub and Challenges for DC Protection

The content in this chapter is based on the following paper:

- G. Bastianel, J. Kircheis, M. Van Deyck, D. Lee, G. Chaffey, M. Vanin, H. Ergun, J. Beerten and D. Van Hertem, “Review, definition and challenges of electrical energy hubs,” in: *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, vol. 226, 2026, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2025.116258>. [15]

2.1 Motivation and Definition of Electrical Energy Hubs

With an increase in the distance of offshore wind farms from shore, the power transmission projects in the North Sea area have shifted from Point-to-Point (PtP) AC [18–21] to PtP HVDC [22–26] links. As HVDC transmission systems are cheaper than AC technologies over long distances [27, 28], and guarantee enhanced power flow controllability and frequency support between asynchronous zones [1], they are currently the preferred option for transmission grid expansion projects related to offshore wind. Moreover, several options for future development of offshore HVDC grids are being proposed, ranging from a central hub with interconnectors [29], to several hub-and-spoke combinations with integrated hydrogen production [30], standardized HVDC PtP links [31] or MTDC/meshed offshore HVDC grids [1, 32, 33]. The last two options coexist in the ENTSO-E Offshore Network De-

velopment Plan [34], where a combination of offshore “*hybrid transmission corridors*” and PtP links is foreseen for the European future grid. In this regard, Elia [12] and Energinet [13, 14] proposed to combine the aggregation of several GW of offshore wind power and its transmission to several European countries via HVDC interconnections in one unit, creating offshore MTDC grids. These ideas follow the concept proposed in [29]. While there seems to be a general understanding of the main principles underlying the goals of these projects [12, 13, 35], there is currently no consistent terminology to address them from a technical perspective. Therefore, in this chapter, the following definition of the term *electrical energy hub* is proposed:

An Electrical Energy Hub (EEH) is a multifunctional node in a power system, managed separately from the main existing control areas, which aggregates local GW-size electrical generation capacity. It is characterized by a high density of electrical equipment and has multiple interconnections to other control areas.

This definition helps to classify EEH projects when clear distinctions are needed, e.g. when defining future planning procedures, grid codes, regulations, and support schemes for EEHs and MTDC grids in general. The development of EEHs implies considerable investments into technologies for which today there is no economy of scale, e.g. HVDC substations, HVDC circuit breakers (DCCB), and HVDC interconnections. A clear definition of the concept could help to accelerate permitting and funding procedures of future projects if their benefit to socio-economic welfare can be quantified and demonstrated. For example, the Projects of Common and Mutual Interest [36] from the European Commission are evaluated with a series of economic key performance indicators [37] and benefit from accelerated permitting procedures and funding.

2.1.1 Electrical Energy Hub Functionalities

Several EEH key *functionalities* are mentioned in the proposed definition and discussed hereafter. Though these functionalities are not necessarily unique to EEHs, their combination creates new challenges for the planning, control, and protection of EEH projects. Note that throughout this chapter, the term “*node*” used in the definition stands for a substation where multiple network elements are connected.

The two main purposes of EEHs are *interconnection*¹ and *aggregation*. *Interconnection* refers to the integration of EEHs across multiple control areas, enabling coordinated power exchanges and enhancing the connectivity of the power system as a whole. *Aggregation* refers to collecting electrical power from several (renewable) energy sources and conditioning it for ef-

¹The “interconnection” and “control area” terms used in this chapter refer to the definitions from the UCTE glossary [38].

efficient transmission, e.g. transferring voltage from 66 kV AC of the wind turbines to ± 525 kV HVDC. Additionally, given the expected multi-GW installed capacity of current grid expansion projects [12–14, 30, 31], EEHs will consist of *multi-GW* electrical substations providing *multiple interconnections* to different control areas. As a result of this large scale and the unique position between interconnected control areas, EEHs are also expected to be *managed separately from the main control areas*, meaning that, though EEHs might be owned or operated by a specific system operator, they are not likely to be considered as an integrated part of the main transmission system. Finally, *aggregation* and *interconnection* are combined in *one unit* and integrate *multiple functionalities* in a small geographical area, implying a *high density of electrical equipment*, which leads to the additional control and protection challenges discussed in Section 2.2. All of the identified functionalities are summarized for clarity in Figure 2.1.

Figure 2.1: An electrical energy hub is defined as “a multifunctional node in a power system, managed separately from the main existing control areas, which aggregates local GW-size electrical generation capacity”, which “is characterized by a high density of electrical equipment and has multiple interconnections to other control areas”. The key functionalities of electrical energy hub projects are highlighted to show their connection to power system operations.

Note that while the concepts described in this chapter should remain applicable to any EEH, the following sections focus on EEHs based on aggregation of offshore wind energy and interconnection of different control areas through HVDC interconnectors, as proposed by the recent projects in the North Sea [12–14].

2.2 Technical Challenges of Electrical Energy Hubs

This section examines individually the protection-related technical challenges associated with EEH projects. These challenges are identified by analyzing the potential implications of the different EEH functionalities for power system operation. In addition, each challenge is related to the specific EEH functionalities defined previously in Figure 2.1, to specific research areas identified as control, planning, and protection, and to possible mitigation measures in Table 2.1.

2.2.1 Limit Maximum Loss of Infeed

Electrical energy hubs are characterized by a multi-GW power transfer capacity. Therefore, outages might cause large power deviations in the connected grids. As a consequence, a protection system is required to prevent faults from causing a loss of infeed (LoI) above the limit set by the dimensioning incident of the main control areas, i.e. the largest single disturbance against which system operators size the reserve capacity and other security measures in their power systems. For example, the maximum LoI in the continental European synchronous area is 3 GW, while it is 1.4 GW in the Nordic power system [39].

As the currently planned EEHs in Europe are based on HVDC interconnections [14, 40], the cost of the protection system is not negligible. HVDC protection equipment is expensive compared to AC equipment and should therefore be considered in the early grid planning stages to avoid excessive costs and over-design [1]. Nevertheless, it should be avoided that the entire power flow through multi-GW EEHs is interrupted even for a limited time (e.g. tens of ms) [41], as the LoI would exceed the dimensioning incident and could cause frequency events in the whole synchronous area connected to it, leading to load shedding or generation curtailment. As a result, (partially) selective HVDC protection is likely to be required in EEHs [2, 7, 42]. This kind of protection system relies on DCCBs that can rapidly interrupt DC fault currents and thus prevent the outage of healthy elements in the system.

Similarly, the control systems of all devices in or connected to the EEH are required to work reliably at any point in time. Malfunctioning controls could lead to the entire trip of the EEH and the subsequent LoI exceeding the dimensioning incident of the power system. Recorded power system events have shown that converter control systems can respond erroneously during faults and frequency excursions, and consequently lead to a subsequent loss of generation and transmission capacity [43–46].

2.2.2 High DC Fault Currents

The concentration of equipment in EEHs may increase the magnitude of DC-side fault currents. Since several HVDC cables and converters are likely to be connected close to each other, DC faults in or in proximity of the EEH will experience high fault currents that rapidly increase due to the capacitive discharge of these components [9, 47]. As a result, additional fault current limiting reactors may be required in EEHs to ensure that fault currents do not exceed the maximum current limits of DCCBs. Moreover, given the GW-size power ratings of EEHs, significant energy dissipation equipment may be required in EEHs to dissipate the energy contained in these fault currents [9]. Opportunities to centralize this energy dissipation equipment may arise depending on the size and topology of the EEH [48]. However, it is expected that both the fault current limiting reactors and energy dissipation equipment will significantly contribute to the protection system costs [49] (and to the system (in)stability for the reactors [50]) and should thus be minimized while considering the constraint of high fault currents in EEHs.

2.2.3 Fault Detection

To guarantee the correct functioning of the HVDC protection system, protection algorithms must detect faults in a limited time, while being secure, i.e. not tripping for faults outside of the protected area, as well as sensitive and dependable, i.e. detecting and tripping faults within the protected area [51]. Since the transient fault phenomena in HVDC grids generally happen on a smaller time scale than in AC grids, specific algorithms, such as traveling wave methods, have been developed for HVDC protection [52]. Moreover, it has been established that in typical multiterminal HVDC grids, algorithms that rely on communication are not applicable due to the long communication delays, especially over long cable distances [53].

However, since EEHs centralize several cables and converters in one location, additional research into the applicability of several algorithms would be required. These studies should evaluate whether typical algorithms are still able to provide the required selectivity given the density of equipment and connections.

The concentration of equipment in one location may also create opportunities for centralized control, as well as faster communication, thus also creating new opportunities for HVDC fault detection that can be investigated for EEHs.

2.2.4 Common Mode Failures

The high density of electrical equipment in an EEH leads to an increased risk for common mode failures, i.e. the failure of multiple systems due to a common cause. Such events can occur in any system due to the malfunctioning of the protection system, e.g. a circuit breaker failure, or by external causes, such as extreme weather events, fire, terrorist attacks, cyber-attacks, etc. [54]. Since EEHs centralize key grid infrastructure in one location - likely with a high density of equipment due to space limitations - it is expected that they are more prone to common mode failures due to externalities. Since the loss of the entire EEH could cause a multi-GW LoI with the possibility of a significant impact on connected AC power systems, specific countermeasures have to be taken into the design to avoid such events. Consequently, system operators may opt to operate certain connections as *normally open*, thus creating physical separations to prevent contingencies from impacting the grid at several locations [55, 56]. In this sense, System Integrity Protection Schemes (SIPS) are usually established to mitigate large system-wide disturbances caused by faults in the power system. Differently from conventional protection systems related to a specific network element, SIPS provides system-wide countermeasures to slow and/or stop cascading outages caused by extreme contingencies [57]. Given that faults in EEHs might lead to large imbalances in the power grids to which they are connected, more dynamic and adaptable SIPS are to be developed. They will be particularly needed to prevent cascading events originating from faults in one of the EEH's network elements.

2.2.5 Interoperability

Interoperability implies that the electrical equipment, e.g. converter stations in MTDC grids, is mutually compatible and interoperable under varying operational modes [58, 59]. As EEHs are centralized multi-GW connection points for HVDC interconnections and RES aggregation, it is expected that further elements could be added in a phased approach, and these elements should be interoperable [60, 61]. Systems today, although containing components from multiple vendors, are developed by one system integrator (typically a manufacturer). As internal functional requirements and interfaces are commonly set in a proprietary or bespoke way, the viability of future expansion by other parties is inherently limited. Moving beyond these turnkey HVDC systems towards systems for which it is feasible for other manufacturers to add elements in a phased manner is therefore essential for large-scale EEHs.

Moreover, addressing interoperability issues implies a need for interoperability on several levels [59, 62]. Functional interoperability is needed such

that devices function correctly together in a system (e.g. converter controls do not adversely interact) [63]. In fact, the physical electrical interface is required to be interoperable, e.g. in voltage, current and power ratings [59]. Furthermore, for effective system design and operation, manufacturer intellectual property concerns must be mitigated to share key information about systems and components for system design [64], as well as for signal interfaces [65]. Communication interfaces must be well defined with common (standardized) protocols [60]. At a fundamental level, system topology should be harmonized, for example which secondary system devices should execute control and protection functions, naturally a precursor to standardized requirements, interfaces and components. Addressing these issues is important to ensure a flexible and modular approach to the design and operation of EEHs. Without agreements on these key interoperability topics the design process is challenging due to both technical reasons, e.g. difficulties in predicting and ensuring the stable integration of components without experiencing interactions or incompatibilities, as well as organizational.

Finally, it is expected that interoperability and viable system expansion can be achieved in future multivendor systems through effective grid codes and standardization [59]. In this manner, a new converter, line, protection IED, or circuit breaker could be added without re-designing the whole system or requiring the involvement of the original manufacturer of other grid elements. However, the industry is still working towards pre-standardization in many fields [61]. Challenges in multi-party development could be mitigated through future harmonized systems engineering methodologies (e.g. model-based system engineering [63], defined as “*the formalised application of modelling to support system requirements, design, analysis, verification and validation activities beginning in the conceptual design phase and continuing throughout development and later life cycle phases*” [66]). It is expected that system operators will increasingly add expandability into the functional requirements of new systems [60], which could be effective as a stepping stone to full HVDC grid codes.

Given the expectations for EEHs’ large-scale energy integration and phased expandability, they are key areas in the HVDC system where multivendor interoperability will be needed. Future EEHs would be expected to be challenged by all of the mentioned interoperability issues, without suitable mitigation through technical solutions governed by grid codes, harmonization and standardization.

2.2.6 Expandability Requirements

As the aggregation of RES and the interconnections to different control areas are expected to keep increasing in a more electrified future, EEHs are

planned to be expandable [35]. To facilitate such expansions, expansion pathways should be developed in early design stages. These pathways give an indication of changes in functional requirements that occur during expansion. For example, to allow the additional cables to be connected to an EEH, besides providing adequate substation space, the system developer should also consider the impact this expansion would have on e.g. the protection strategy requirements. Such changes in protection requirements further impact the substation lay-out, as additional DCCBs and reactors would possibly be required, but also may have implications for the converter fault-ride-through capabilities [67]. These changes are expected to be challenging to implement, especially offshore, given that EEHs are likely to have a high concentration of equipment and are consequently not suitable for the replacement and redesign of existing components. Therefore, expansions should be foreseen during the original planning stage of the project, to guarantee that the additional equipment can be safely installed and operated within the EEH context.

Note that while discussing the regulatory and market design aspects of EEHs is beyond the scope of this report, it is worth mentioning that recent work [68–74] have discussed the impact of different market designs, e.g. home market, single offshore bidding zone, etc., on the overall EEHs' socio-economic welfare. All the above-mentioned references advocate for an Offshore Bidding Zone market design. While the optimal market design might be case-dependent, its general goal is that the investment cost for society should be minimized while guaranteeing that the owners of the generation assets are remunerated for their investments and the risk associated to them.

Table 2.1: Electrical energy hubs are characterized by several key functionalities, i.e. *aggregation, high density of electrical equipment, interconnection, multi-GW, multiple functionalities, one unit, and separate and independent control from the main control areas*. These functionalities are related to each identified relevant technical challenge, and assigned to one or more main research areas between *control, planning, and protection* of electrical energy hubs. In addition, possible mitigation measures for each technical challenge are proposed.

Technical challenge	Related functionalities	Main research area	Mitigation measures
Grid congestion	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Aggregation • Interconnection • Multi-GW 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Planning 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Generation redispatch • Grid topology optimization
Limit maximum loss of infeed	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Aggregation • Multi-GW 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Control • Planning • Protection 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Selective HVDC protection • Contingency-resilient control
High DC fault currents	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Multi-GW • High density of electrical equipment • One unit 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Protection 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fault current limiting reactors • Energy dissipation equipment
Fault detection	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High density of electrical equipment • One unit 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Protection 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fast protection algorithms • Centralized protection control
Common mode failure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High density of electrical equipment • Interconnection • One unit 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Control • Protection 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Preventive reconfiguration • System integrity protection schemes
Control interactions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High density of electrical equipment • Interconnection • One unit 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Control 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Detailed EMT analysis • Clear design specification of components
Interoperability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High density of electrical equipment • One unit 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Control • Protection 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Common communication protocols • Standardized secondary systems • Effective grid codes • Model-based system engineering
Expandability requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Aggregation • High density of electrical equipment • Interconnection • Multiple functionalities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Control • Planning • Protection 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Expandable grid topology planning • Functional requirements for expandable protection systems

Chapter 3

Protection Configuration Shortlisting for HVDC Switching Stations and Electrical Energy Hubs

The content in this chapter is based on the following paper:

- M. Van Deyck, G. Chaffey and D. Van Hertem, “Shortlisting Protection Configurations for HVDC Grids and Electrical Energy Hubs,” arXiv:2505.05886. [16]

3.1 Introduction

Recent declarations by surrounding countries aim to transform the North Sea into *Europe’s green power plant* [11]. To achieve this, these countries aim to increase offshore wind capacity to 300 GW by 2050. Significant transmission infrastructure investments will be required, both onshore and offshore, to integrate these vast amounts of offshore energy into the existing power systems.

The prospective development of offshore multiterminal HVDC (MTDC) grids offers flexible transmission capacity, well suited for high power capacities and long distances [27]. The electrical energy hub concept - commonly also known as *energy islands* - is expected to become an important aspect of these MTDC grids in the future [15]. In these hubs, offshore equipment can be centralized to serve both as a central node in interconnected MTDC grids, and for the large-scale integration of renewable energy sources. Multi-GW offshore energy hubs are under development in Belgium [40] and Den-

mark [13, 75] and have been considered for several other countries [76].

The protection of MTDC grids has been a key obstacle to the realization of these systems [1]. The choice of a *protection strategy* is a key step in the planning of future MTDC grids [3, 7]. These strategies (fully selective, non-selective, and partially selective protection) dictate the selectivity of the protection system and consequently have a large influence on the protection equipment requirements and the impact of DC faults.

3.1.1 Existing Protection Design Methodologies

HVDC circuit breakers (DCCB) are significantly more complex and expensive than AC breakers. Therefore, several methodologies exist for assessing the need for these breakers in MTDC grids. In [3, 7], different implementations of the fundamental protection strategies are considered for a four terminal benchmark network. A comparison of these strategies and implementations is performed based on protection performance metrics such as component count, AC grid impact, risk analysis and extensibility. Time-domain electromagnetic transient (EMT) simulations generate a thorough understanding of the transient fault response related to each strategy implementation. Though this method allows a detailed comparison of possible protection implementations for an MTDC grid, it relies on expert-based selections of the possible protection strategies and implementations. The use of EMT studies to compare these options brings little generic insights and imposes a high computational load on the design, which will significantly increase when the network size increases [77].

A protection design approach for a larger MTDC grid that consists of multiple interconnected offshore electrical energy hubs is presented in [42, 78]. The protection design is carried out in a modular way based on a cost-benefit analysis methodology from [79]. A standardized DC-side busbar topology and protection strategy are determined based on estimated costs, AC grid constraints and fault ride through capabilities of offshore wind farms. Load flow studies and EMT simulations are performed to dimension the DC reactors. The protection design is standardized such that it can be uniformly applied, leading to an implementation of the fully selective strategy in each hub. This modular approach is time efficient for designing the protection system for several electrical energy hubs, since the cost-benefit analysis and component sizing is only performed once. However it is unclear whether the chosen protection configuration is actually the ideal option for every hub. It seems likely that better options may exist for specific hubs and that these may vary since different AC grid requirements, fault ride through capabilities or energy hub sizes may apply across the system. Therefore, a protection design approach that facilitates the efficient design of several hubs while con-

sidering the specific context of each system may improve the overall HVDC protection design.

Methodologies for HVDC protection design based primarily on AC grid frequency stability limits have been proposed in [8, 41, 80]. These methods evaluate protection strategies by considering the loss of power transfer capacity during the fault clearing process. Depending on the duration of this power flow interruption, the frequency change in the AC grid can be calculated. By taking into account frequency stability limits, this results in strict limitations of the protection zone size, which follows from the protection strategy choice, and of the operating time of the DC protection and grid restoration sequence. In [8], this method is used for a techno-economic evaluation of the non-selective and fully selective strategies based on the expected costs for protection equipment and frequency containment reserves required to maintain AC grid stability. The evaluation of loss of power transfer capacity is an efficient method to evaluate possible DC fault impacts that does not require detailed time-domain simulations. As a result, many possible designs, operational scenarios or network configurations can be considered in this way.

These methodologies focus on applying a fundamental protection strategy to a predefined HVDC grid topology. However, the system-level application of a protection strategy does not inherently describe the full implementation of the protection system. For example, the partially selective protection strategy implies that part of the MTDC grid remains in continuous operation while another part, containing the faulted element, is de-energized as the fault is cleared [3]. This principle can be implemented in several ways in heavily meshed grids or radial grids with many connections. Moreover, other configurations that are not fully described by fundamental protection strategies, e.g. preventive grid reconfiguration [55], can be used together with other protection strategies to improve the effectiveness of the DC protection system, meaning that low fault impacts are achieved for low protection system costs.

3.1.2 Contribution and Outline

The arrangement of different connections, and particularly the inclusion of DCCBs between these connections, is expected to become an important factor in the DC protection design of future MTDC grids with large HVDC switching stations (DCSS) and electrical energy hubs. This design of the protection *configuration* encompasses more than is typically described by fundamental protection strategies and leads to a complex design problem with a large number of permutations. However, this design method offers a more open approach to HVDC protection design. It ensures that installed equip-

ment is efficiently utilized and over-investments are avoided.

This approach to protection configuration design introduces many possible options, especially as the number of lines, converters and DCCBs increase. Consequently, performing detailed time-domain studies or techno-economic cost-benefit analyses for each configuration would not be possible since, depending on the network size, millions of configurations would have to be evaluated. Therefore, this chapter proposes a shortlisting approach that selects suitable HVDC switching station configurations based on high-level indicators related to possible DC fault impacts. After this initial shortlisting, detailed component-level studies can be performed to complete the full substation and protection design. With this approach, MTDC grid developers can design protection systems with a focus on specific DCSS, rather than applying grid-level strategies. By focusing on the high-level configuration in this initial stage, it also becomes easier to perform the (co-)design of large systems consisting of several hubs [10]. The full shortlisting methodology is explained in Section 3.2. In Section 3.3, the method is applied to three test cases, which represent electrical energy hubs of different sizes.

3.2 Protection Configuration Shortlisting Methodology

This section describes the models and methods used for shortlisting protection configurations. A graph-based representation of electrical energy hubs that allows efficient fault impact calculations is proposed. The principles of the fault clearing method are then explained, followed by the key assumptions of the method. The shortlisting process is then described generally, after which a generic electrical energy hub test case is used to illustrate the method in the final subsection.

3.2.1 Modeling Approach

The arrangement of protection zones in an MTDC grid is crucial to the HVDC protection design. These zones are bordered by elements that can interrupt DC fault currents, e.g. DCCBs or fault-blocking converters. Without these fault-blocking components, DC fault currents cannot be interrupted by typical AC switchgear due to their lack of natural zero crossings. Consequently, if a fault occurs within a protection zone, all elements in this zone must be de-energized for a short time, allowing the faulted element to be cleared at near-zero current by mechanical switchgear such as high-speed disconnectors [81]. In typical HVDC protection designs, the size of the protection zones, and the number of elements which need to be de-energized during

the fault clearance, are determined by the protection strategy, i.e. the entire HVDC grid for the non-selective strategy, part of the grid in the partially selective strategy and only the faulted element in the fully selective strategy [7]. By allowing healthy parts of the grid to remain in continuous operation while the fault is cleared, selective protection strategies reduce the momentary loss of active power infeed into AC grids, limiting the risk of frequency deviations in these grids [41, 80].

HVDC protection designs can be evaluated based on the protection zones resulting from the configuration of converters, cables and DCCBs and by evaluating possible fault impacts. These can be quantified by the *worst-case loss of power transfer*. This metric (P_{LoI} in Eq. (3.1)) is defined as the maximum Loss of Infeed (LoI), i.e. the difference in power flow before and during the fault ($P_{PreFault}$ and P_{Fault}), in each connected AC grid (G), caused by a fault in any protection zone (z).

$$P_{LoI} = \max_z \left(\sum_G P_{PreFault,G} - P_{Fault,G,z} \right) \quad (3.1)$$

The worst-case loss of power transfer metric is related to the AC grid frequency stability, but does not require detailed knowledge of the AC grid inertia, grid loading and configuration, or of the DC protection operating time. Consequently, protection configurations can be compared in a simplified manner. Since detailed grid models are not required for this, a graph-based representation of the HVDC and AC grids is used to represent the configuration of the grid before and during the faulted state.

Fig. 3.1 shows an example electrical energy hub test case represented as a system-level diagram in Fig. 3.1a and using a graph-based representation in Fig. 3.1b. This example network consists of an electrical energy hub (EEH), indicated by the dashed box, with two parallel converter stations and four connections to three different synchronous AC grids. In both diagrams, converters and HVDC cables are indicated in yellow and red respectively. This network topology resembles early energy hub designs in Belgium and Denmark and consequently serves as a representation for near-future electrical energy hubs. Since, further in the future, electrical energy hubs are expected to increase in size, this example is termed the *small test case*. A *medium-* and *large test case* are introduced for additional analysis in Section 3.3. Although a per-pole representation is used here, any configuration, e.g. monopolar or bipolar, can be used in the actual design. The case studies in this report consider a bipolar converter configuration.

The proposed network model represents key elements in the grid, as relevant to protection studies, i.e. cables, converters and switchgear (blue lines in Fig. 3.1b) as edges between graph nodes. Electrical network configurations can be varied by changing the nodes at which each edge is connected.

Figure 3.1: Per-pole representation of an example electrical energy hub test case representing near-future designs.

In the diagrams in Fig. 3.1, the DC side of the electrical energy hub (DC EEH) is not explicitly depicted since the design of this area will be determined by the protection configuration design method.

Nodes and edges are characterized as *internal*, i.e. on the electrical energy hub (green nodes in Fig. 3.1b), or *external* (blue nodes in Fig. 3.1b) and as AC or DC, i.e. connected to the AC or DC side of the network.

A *fault-blocking* characteristic is assigned to edges in the graph model that represent circuit breakers or other fault blocking elements, indicating that fault currents can be interrupted there. This allows the calculation of *protection zones* based on the location of these fault-blocking edges. Consequently, any configuration of protection zones can be achieved by varying the location of these fault-blocking edges and the connections of converter and cable edges to the DC nodes in the electrical energy hub.

External AC nodes represent different synchronous systems connected to the electrical energy hub. In future systems, electrical energy hubs may be connected to a larger multiterminal HVDC grid containing additional electrical energy hubs. Though the examples illustrated here focus on a single electrical energy hub, these larger HVDC grids with multiple energy hubs can be considered using the proposed shortlisting method.

These simplified representations of HVDC and AC grids and of the HVDC protection designs allow the creation and evaluation of large numbers of electrical energy hub topologies and protection implementations. Therefore, though this modeling approach does not give the full detail of the technical implications of grid topologies and protection designs, it is effective for shortlisting. Consequently, this shortlisting step serves as a precursor to more detailed protection design studies. In these studies, selected configurations and topologies can subsequently be used to perform component-level

detailed design and analysis in e.g. EMT simulation [10].

3.2.2 Fault Impact Evaluation

The graph-based network modeling approach is used to compare grid topologies and protection designs by evaluating worst-case fault impacts for different DC protection configurations. By evaluating the fault-blocking characteristics of the edges in the graph model, the network can be split into sub-graphs representing the protection zones, as depicted in Fig. 3.2a-3.2b where an example configuration with one DCCB is used. HVDC protection operates such that the full protection zone is de-energized if any element within that zone is faulted. Therefore, the network can be represented in the faulted state by removing the sub-graph containing the faulted element from the pre-fault graph as exemplified in Fig. 3.2c for an example fault anywhere in Protection Zone 1. In the post-fault state, it is assumed that the faulted element is removed from the system and the remaining elements in the grid are re-energized and reconnected to the grid, as represented in Fig. 3.2d for an example cable fault.

Fig. 3.3 illustrates an example time-domain representation of the fault clearing process. The figure shows the available controlled active power per cable, out of the maximum cable rating P , during the fault clearing process for a cable in a healthy protection zone (green), a healthy cable in the faulted protection zone (blue), and the faulted cable (red). The faulted state of the network lasts from the opening of the DCCBs and the splitting of the grid into healthy and unhealthy protection zones at t_{sp} until the reconnection of healthy grid elements at t_{ReCon} which follows the fault clearing and converter deblocking. Though the exact duration of this fault clearing process depends on many factors such as the exact fault location and grid configuration, it can be estimated that the grid operates in the faulted state for up to several seconds [82].

Using this modeling approach for faults, their impact is evaluated by calculating the loss of active power transfer between the electrical energy hub and onshore AC grids in the pre-fault and faulted states, as represented by Eq. (3.1). The electrical characteristics of the grid, i.e. the voltages at each node and the impedance of the branches, are not included in the models. Therefore, a different approach is used to model the power flows. This approach relies on the *capacity* and *length* characteristics of graph edges and on predefined infeed and demand capacities at the AC nodes¹. To ensure that

¹More complex power flow scenarios can be implemented if additional offshore wind farms or connected electrical energy hubs are considered, i.e. by defining additional infeed capacity at external DC nodes. This may lead to a more accurate representation of the expected power flows in the grid, though this evaluation is left out of the scope of this

Figure 3.2: Grid representation for the evaluation of fault impacts.

Figure 3.3: Availability of controlled active power during the fault clearing and restoration process on a cable in the healthy protection zone (green), on a healthy cable in the faulted protection zone (blue, dashed) and on the faulted cable (red).

the considered faults lead to the highest loss of power transfer, and thus represent worst-case fault impacts, the grid is assumed to be maximally loaded. Any operational scenario where the grid is operated below the maximum rating would consequently lead to a lower total LoI and lower total fault impacts. Different power flow scenarios are created by changing the direction of power flow to and from the different AC nodes. By evaluating different power flow scenarios, it can be ensured that all relevant fault cases are considered and that the selected protection configuration operates effectively in each one.

In the illustrative examples in this chapter, it is assumed that all cables and converters have the same capacity of $1P$, e.g. 1 GW (per pole in a bipolar system). The loss of power transfer in different fault scenarios and protection configurations can therefore be expressed in terms of multiples of P , making the method applicable for systems of different ratings and in different configurations. Mixed systems, i.e. systems with multiple ratings or combinations of monopolar and bipolar systems with or without a dedicated metallic return can also be considered. In rigid bipolar systems with no metallic return, a pole-to-ground cable fault results in a $2P$ loss of power transfer capacity, since both poles are affected. Similarly, pole-to-pole faults cause twice the impact of pole-to-ground faults in bipolar grids with a dedicated metallic return. By integrating these aspects in the protection shortlisting methodology, complex systems can be evaluated. However, in this chapter, the illustration of the method on the example test cases is limited to the single-pole representation of a system where each outage causes a permanent capacity reduction of $1P$.

Under these assumptions, the demand and infeed settings for the example grid test case can, for example, be set as listed in Tab. 3.1. In specific grid topologies where the total transmission capacity exceeds the infeed capacity on the electrical energy hub, the grid can be fully loaded by allowing onshore grids to export additional power. The onshore grid fulfilling this role can be varied to achieve different power flow scenarios that each fully load the HVDC grid.

Given a set of power infeed and demand settings, a graph theory-based shortest path algorithm that is adapted to include available line capacity is used to match demand and infeed nodes and thus create indicative possible power flow scenarios for the fault impact analyses. Power flows are created in this way for the pre-fault and faulted network. In the faulted state, the available transmission capacity is reduced, which means that not all demand in the AC grid nodes can be satisfied, causing a momentary loss of infeed. By calculating this LoI in different electrical energy hub configurations, the efficiency of the protection design is evaluated.

conceptual chapter.

Table 3.1: Example infeed and demand settings in the small test case example, leading to a maximal grid loading.

Node	Infeed (+) / Demand (-)
AC_1	$+2P$
AC_6	$-2P$
AC_7	$+1P$
AC_9	$-1P$

3.2.3 Model Assumptions

The representation of AC and HVDC grids, faults, and the fault clearing process described in the previous subsections, offers a simplified method to evaluate fault impacts with enough detail to compare different electrical energy hub protection designs based on the configuration of the protection zones. However, this simplified representation makes some technical assumptions of which the most important are summarized in this subsection. The succession of pre-fault, faulted and post-fault states assumes a protection system that can detect, locate, and interrupt fault currents. In addition, it is assumed that the grid elements outside the faulted protection zone remain in continuous operation, allowing the power flow to persist in the remaining grid elements in the faulted-state network. This assumption may influence some detailed aspects of the protection system implementation, such as converter fault ride through requirements and DC protection coordination, that do not typically need to be considered at this stage of the design [9]. During the faulted and post-fault states, it is, moreover, assumed that the infeed and demand setpoints, as well as the converter operating points, are equal to the pre-fault grid state. This entails that the generators located at infeeding nodes, such as (offshore) wind farms, ride through the network faults without the need for power curtailment, as long as sufficient network capacity is available. It also means that no automatic actions are taken to decrease the demand in onshore grids as a means to limit the fault impact, e.g. reserve activation or demand curtailment.

In grid codes, the maximum loss of infeed is limited by the *dimensioning incident*, stating that no installations may be connected if they have the potential to cause outages exceeding this limit, as they have the potential to cause intolerable frequency instabilities leading to black-outs. Consequently, it is assumed that limiting the loss of active power infeed, in worst-case fault conditions, is an accurate metric for the comparison of different protection designs [41]. In reality, the frequency instability of AC grids caused by a loss of active power infeed depends on several factors, such as the total grid inertia, the availability of frequency containment reserves, and the use of load

curtailment [8, 80]. Moreover, other AC grid aspects, i.e. transient stability and voltage stability, may be influenced by HVDC grid faults, but are less accurately represented by the loss of active power infeed. However, the loss of reactive power capability caused by DC grid faults can be modeled similarly to the possible loss of active power by evaluating the availability of converters during the faulted state of the grid. Nevertheless, in depth studies are required during the final phases of the HVDC grid design to assess the actual AC grid impacts of the active and reactive power losses. However, for the performed protection configuration shortlisting studies, the representation of this impact as momentary loss of infeed is sufficient.

3.2.4 Configuration Selection Process

Using the graph-based modeling and fault impact evaluation method, different electrical energy hub configurations and protection designs can be generated and compared to create a shortlist of viable designs. The options are created by varying the connection points of HVDC cables, converters, and the mutual connections between the internal DC nodes in the electrical energy hub network model. The number of connected cables, converters, and the topology of the external grid are seen as inputs from the system designer that specify the overall constraints for the network and electrical energy hub for which the protection configuration is selected. Consequently, the shortlisting algorithm can be used to find the most effective configuration, from a protection standpoint, for a given energy hub size - represented by the number of cables and converters - and complexity or investment cost, represented by the DCCB count. This means that the number of included DCCBs can either be set as an input from the system designer, or the shortlisting can be performed for each DCCB count, allowing the effect of adding more DCCBs to be evaluated by comparing the selected configurations and fault impacts for different DCCB counts.

The shortlisting methodology consists of an iterative process, starting with the creation of all possible configurations as graph networks and subsequently selecting those that achieve the lowest LoI in worst-case fault conditions in different power flow scenarios. The number of evaluated configurations depends on the electrical energy hub size and the allowed number of DCCBs. Cables in a single protection zone can be considered to be connected to the same node on the electrical energy hub from a protection zone point of view. This means that, although some switchgear other than DCCBs may be implemented between these connections, they are essentially seen as being connected to a single busbar. Consequently, the number of DC nodes in the electrical energy hub graph is equal to the number of protection zones achieved by the DCCB configuration. The total number of configura-

tions is then set by the number of ways the converter and cable edges can be connected to the DC nodes, rising along with the converter and cable count. Moreover, the number of possible DC node configurations increases strongly if more DCCBs are allowed, further increasing the number of configurations that should be considered in the shortlisting process. This results in a very large set of N possible configurations where N can be expressed as

$$N = N_{con} \cdot (N_{DC,con})^{N_{cab} + N_{conv}}, \quad (3.2)$$

with N_{con} the number of configurations that can be created with a certain number of DCCBs (N_{DC}) e.g. if three DCCBs are used, three configurations can be created, i.e a star, delta or line arrangement. $N_{DC,con}$ represents the number of DC nodes for a specific configuration and is limited to

$$N_{DC,con} \leq N_{CB} + 1, \quad (3.3)$$

with N_{CB} the number of DCCBs. As each converter and cable edge can be connected to any DC node, the number of possible configurations rises exponentially with the number of cables N_{cab} and converters in the electrical energy hub N_{conv} as shown in Eq. (3.2).

The many possible configurations and the exponential increase in options as systems grow are clear indicators of the need to shortlist these design options. Consequently, the simplified network models are ideal for representing these large numbers of configurations, though the tractability of the algorithm is also limited when larger systems (i.e. with more than six cables or DCCBs) are evaluated. However, the initial solution size N can be reduced, e.g. by eliminating configurations that do not utilize all available DC nodes and are thus identical to solutions with fewer breakers, or by eliminating options based on symmetry.

3.2.5 Test Case Illustration

The shortlisting methodology is illustrated for three generic test cases, representing increasing energy hub sizes. Each of these cases has the same basic external network configuration, consisting of HVDC links between the electrical energy hub and three onshore grids. This configuration of the external HVDC grid is chosen to represent the context of several proposed electrical energy hub projects in Europe, which are expected to host interconnections to up to three different synchronous areas while integrating large capacities of offshore wind power into these onshore grids [15]. As these projects are expected to increase in size in the future, the chosen test cases have both an increasing capacity of connected cables and offshore wind capacity at the electrical energy hub. Tab. 3.2 lists the number of converters in the electrical energy hub and cable connections to each onshore grid (per pole) for

each test case. The system-level diagram for the small test case is depicted in Fig. 3.1a and introduced for the medium and large test cases in Fig. 3.4a and 3.4b.

Figure 3.4: System-level diagram for medium and large electrical energy hub test case.

Table 3.2: Parameters (per pole) for the considered test cases.

Test Case	Internal Converters	Connections to		
		AC grid 1	AC grid 2	AC grid 3
Small	2	2	1	1
Medium	3	2	2	2
Large	6	2	2	2

The shortlisting process filters electrical energy hub configurations by evaluating the fault impact in different power flow scenarios. In this chapter, the method is illustrated for the example test cases using three example power flow scenarios (PF_1 - PF_3). The converters on the electrical energy hub are assumed to feed power into the HVDC grid at their rated capacity, representing high wind infeed scenarios. The remaining power flows are then varied by changing which onshore grid acts as a net exporter, leading to the three power flow scenarios as depicted by Fig. 3.5. In the small and medium test cases, these power flow scenarios accurately describe the different possible conditions for high-impact faults in high wind infeed conditions. However, in the large test case, only one power flow scenario is considered, as the wind infeed from the electrical energy hub is enough to fully load the system and no external export grid is required.

In each considered power flow scenario, electrical energy hub configurations are selected that achieve the lowest total worst-case loss of power transfer, as well as the lowest impact per AC zone. Given the three considered power flow scenarios, this results in six basic filtering steps in which

Figure 3.5: Example power flow scenarios used to illustrate the shortlisting process.

the number of applicable electrical energy hub configurations can be significantly reduced. However, further reductions can be made if necessary by filtering the configuration options based on additional metrics, rather than only the worst-case loss of power transfer. Fig. 3.6 illustrates these filtering steps.

Figure 3.6: Filtering steps in the considered example of the shortlisting methodology.

3.3 Results

3.3.1 Filtering Outcomes

The shortlisting process is demonstrated in this section for the three considered test cases. For each case, configurations with up to five DCCBs are considered, resulting in a large number of evaluated configurations, especially for the large test case.

Using the shortlisting methodology, the possible configurations can be drastically reduced, retaining only the design options that achieve minimal worst-case fault impacts in the considered power flow scenarios, i.e. *lowest impact configurations*. Only these lowest impact configurations are then evaluated in subsequent filtering steps using different fault impact metrics and power flow scenarios. After considering all metrics and power flows, the

final set of lowest impact configurations represent the most effective protection configurations for the considered DCSS.

(a) Small test case

(b) Medium test case

(c) Large test case

Figure 3.7: Total worst-case loss of power transfer in each considered power flow scenario in the example electrical energy hub test cases for the selected lowest impact configurations.

Fig. 3.7 shows the worst-case loss of power transfer to all onshore grids in the lowest impact configurations in each power flow scenario. This figure shows that, to reduce the fault impact to $1P$ in all power flow conditions, the small test case requires at least three DCCBs while the medium and large cases need at least five. However, if fewer DCCBs are used, it is possible in some cases to reduce the impact only for specific power flow scenarios. This result highlights the influence of power flows on the performance of the protection system. Consequently, the ability to separately consider and prioritize power flows is an advantage of the proposed shortlisting method, compared to system-level protection strategy-based choices.

3.3.2 Additional Filtering Metrics

Besides the worst-case loss of power transfer, any metric that relies on the connectivity of the HVDC grid before and during the faulted state can be applied in the proposed methodology. These metrics can either be used in

place of the worst-case impact metric or to carry out additional filtering steps after the initial selection of lowest impact configurations. Examples of additional metrics are the availability of reactive power during faults, i.e. the continuous operation of offshore and onshore converters, or the preferred configuration if specific network expansions are expected in the future. Here, two other additional metrics are introduced: *length-weighted expected fault impact* and *average impact of primary protection failure*. The results for these metrics applied to the considered test cases for power flow scenario PF_1 are shown in Fig. 3.8.

The length-weighted expected fault impact metric (P_{avg}) represents the expected impact of faults rather than the worst-case. Since it could be estimated that the failure rate of an HVDC cable is approximately proportional to the length, the expected fault impact can simply be evaluated by averaging the impact of every cable fault (c), weighted by the length of each cable (L_c) compared to the total length of all cables in the system (L_{tot}) as shown in Eq. (3.4).

$$P_{avg} = \sum_c \left(\frac{L_c}{L_{tot}} \cdot \sum_G P_{PreFault,G} - P_{Fault,G,c} \right) \quad (3.4)$$

In the considered test cases, the length-weighted expected impact metric is applied to the selected topologies after the initial filtering steps (which evaluate the maximum impact) with cable lengths assumed as 100 km, 700 km and 250 km for connections to AC grids 1, 2 and 3 respectively.

The second additional metric is the average loss of active power transfer in case of primary protection failure (P_{bu}), i.e. in case the *back-up* protection needs to operate. The failure of a primary DCCB to interrupt a fault is assumed. This can be caused by a malfunction of the breaker itself or the controlling protection algorithms. It is assumed here that the fault is, in this case, interrupted by adjacent DCCBs or AC circuit breakers, causing a larger portion of the HVDC grid to be de-energized. The impact of primary protection failure is calculated as the average loss of power transfer caused by the worst-case cable fault (c) for every primary breaker failure (PB):

$$P_{bu} = \frac{1}{N_{CB}} \cdot \sum_{PB} \left(\max_c \left(\sum_G P_{PreFault,G} - P_{Fault,G,c,PB} \right) \right) \quad (3.5)$$

3.3.3 Discussion of Results

The protection configuration shortlisting methodology has been applied to three test cases that represent example electrical energy hub networks of increasing sizes. The need for an efficient filtering process follows from the

(a) Small test case

(b) Medium test case

(c) Large test case

Figure 3.8: Length-weighted expected impact and average impact of primary protection failure in the considered electrical energy hub test cases for the selected protection configurations.

(a) Small test case

(b) Medium test case

(c) Large test case

Figure 3.9: Number of possible protection configurations in the considered electrical energy hub test cases at different stages of the filtering process. The additional metric evaluations are executed in parallel and drawn as separate lines if the results differ.

number of possible configurations, which becomes increasingly large - even after preemptively eliminating illogical cases - especially in electrical energy hubs with many connections and DCCBs. In cases with many initial options, many configurations remain after the initial filtering steps. However, by using additional metrics for protection design evaluation in the filtering process, the lowest impact configurations can be further reduced until only configurations that function identically from a protection perspective remain. The filtering process and the reduction of possible protection configurations are summarized in Fig. 3.9 where the number of lowest impact configurations is shown (on a logarithmic scale) for each filtering step.

Besides being a method for efficient electrical energy hub design, the shortlisting methodology allows system designers to evaluate how many DCCBs are required in the system to achieve a certain maximum fault impact, while ensuring that DCCBs are efficiently placed. The additional metrics can also be applied to further differentiate between different DCCB counts. The total worst-case fault impact results, shown in Fig. 3.7 show that, in the small test case, no difference in impact is achieved by increasing the DCCB count beyond three. Similarly, in the medium and large cases, there is no reduction in worst-case impact if two or four DCCBs are used compared to the selected configurations with one fewer breaker. However, in these cases, increasing the DCCB count reduces the length-weighted average impact or the average impact of primary protection failure, as shown by Fig. 3.8. Thus, different DCCB counts can be evaluated based on these metrics.

By evaluating these different levels of protection represented by increasing DCCB counts, the priorities for protection designs can be studied. Fig. 3.10 illustrates these principles by representing the lowest impact configurations for the small test case as heat maps. These heat maps show how often elements (converters and cables) are connected in the same protection zones. Fig. 3.10a shows that, if only one DCCB is implemented, it is used to separate each converter on the electrical energy hub, as well as the two cables connecting to AC grid 1 into different protection zones. Figures 3.10b and 3.10c show that this principle is maintained even if more DCCBs are included. The separation of these power flow paths from the energy hub converters to the AC grid with two connected cables shows both the importance of minimizing the fault impact per synchronous area, as well as the prioritization of the first two considered power flows, which both feed power into AC grid 1. Fig. 3.10a also shows that Cables 3 and 4, connecting to AC grids 2 and 3 respectively are divided over the two protection zones created by the one DCCB, thus explaining why, in the scenario where all power flows to these two AC grids, PF_3 , the impact can be minimized to $1P$. It can be seen in Figures 3.7a and 3.10b that putting Cables 3 and 4 in one separate protection zone by using an extra DCCB reduces the worst-case fault impact in PF_1 and

PF_2 while it is increased in PF_3 . Fig. 3.10c shows that, only if all cables connecting to onshore AC grids are separated into different protection zones, the fault impact can be minimized to $1P$ in every power flow scenario.

Figure 3.10: Number of times elements are located in the same protection zone in the lowest impact configurations in the small test case. Label colors represent connected AC grids.

Though it is evident that impacts can be minimized by connecting each component in a different protection zone if several DCCBs are used, the results in Fig. 3.10 also show less obvious principles regarding protection design with fewer DCCBs. A similar evaluation can be made for the medium and large test cases. This is illustrated in Tab. 3.3 which lists, for each test case, the proportion of lowest impact cases² for all considered breaker counts to which the following design principles apply:

1. Cables to the same AC grid are separated in different protection zones
2. All converters in the EEH are separated in different protection zones.
3. PF_1 is prioritized by connecting cables to AC grid 1 in the same protection zone as EEH converters
4. PF_1 is prioritized by separating connections to AC grid 1 from other cables

The results in Tab. 3.3 highlight the key principles for the considered test cases. It is shown that, in the lowest impact configurations, connections to the same AC grid are always separated and that converters in the electrical energy hub are also often connected in separate protection zones. Additionally, the power flow to AC grid 1 is prioritized in different ways. In the small and large test cases, connections to AC grid 1 are always placed in the same protection zone as converters. In the medium test case, connections to AC

²After the full filtering process, including the average expected impact additional metric.

grid 1 are usually separated from other connections. While these analyses provide insights into the design principles for the considered test cases, future work considering various additional test cases could lead to more generally applicable protection design rules.

Table 3.3: Occurrence rate of proposed design principles in lowest impact configurations after shortlisting.

Principle	Small	Medium	Large
(1)	100%	100%	100%
(2)	100%	97.3%	81.7%
(3)	100%	51.4%	100%
(4)	66.7%	91.9%	81.7%

3.3.4 Evaluation of Fully Selective Configurations

In the performed case studies, protection configurations with up to five DC-CBs are considered. This allows each cable, in the largest considered test cases, to be connected in a separate protection zone with respect to other cable connections. Although the implementations of traditional protection strategies are not uniquely defined in an electrical energy hub or an MTDC grid with many centralized connections, example configurations resembling these strategies can be compared with the configurations that are selected by the full shortlisting process. Based on the conclusions from [42], a possible implementation of the fully selective strategy can be considered in which a DCCB is included on each cable or line connection on the electrical energy hub, but not at the converter connections. By implementing this specific configuration according to the network modeling methodology used in the shortlisting process, the results for this specific implementation in the small, medium and large test cases are calculated. The achieved impacts with this configuration and the required number of DCCBs are listed for the considered power flow scenarios and additional metrics in Tab. 3.4. These results show that the typical fully selective strategy maximally limits the maximum worst case and average expected fault impact but is subject to very high fault impacts in case of primary protection failure. Moreover, if these results are compared to the impacts achieved in the configurations selected by the shortlisting method, as displayed in Fig. 3.7 and 3.8, it becomes clear that the same worst case and average fault impacts can be achieved with one fewer DCCB, while the impact of primary protection failure is also reduced compared to the fully selective implementation. This demonstrates the importance of considering the protection configuration as proposed in this report, instead of

implementing fixed protection strategies.

Table 3.4: Fault impacts in the configuration from [42] compared to shortlisting results (**bold**) where different.

Test case	DCCBs	PF_1	PF_2	PF_3	AVG	BU
Small	4 (3)	1P	1P	1P	1P	3P (1.66P)
Medium	6 (5)	1P	1P	1P	0.33P	4P (1P)
Large	6 (5)	1P	1P	1P	1P	6P (2P)

In future studies, the protection configuration shortlisting methodology will be used for further evaluations of proposed HVDC switching station designs.

3.4 Conclusion

The presented shortlisting approach for protection configurations in electrical energy hubs offers a new method for HVDC protection system design. This method integrates the configuration of DCCBs and the connection of HVDC converters and cables into the system design during early development stages of electrical energy hubs or HVDC switching stations. Reduced-order models are used to evaluate large quantities of protection configurations, including possible designs that are not described by typical protection strategies. Consequently, a more open approach to the protection design is adopted by considering every possible protection configuration option. These options are assessed based on several fault impact metrics using a simplified fault impact calculation method that does not require a detailed analysis of the HVDC or AC grids.

The fault impact results generated during the shortlisting process allow system developers to decide on the required investment into HVDC protection equipment by evaluating impacts in different scenarios. Since the filtering method selects only the configurations that achieve the lowest impacts with a given DCCB count, it is also ensured that equipment is efficiently used for the considered fault scenarios.

When applied to three example electrical energy hub test cases, it is shown that the shortlisting methodology facilitates a strong reduction in the number of possible protection configurations through the iterative filtering process.

The selected lowest impact configurations at the end of the filtering process show that the protection configuration should generally place connections to one AC grid in different protection zones and maximally separate

the most relevant power flow paths. Moreover, the comparison of a typical implementation of the fully selective strategy to the configurations selected by the shortlisting methodology shows that the proposed approach leads to improved protection designs that, with fewer DCCBs than the typically considered implementation of the fully selective strategy, equally limit the worst-case and average impact of faults, while resulting in lower fault impacts in case of primary protection failure.

Chapter 4

Techno-Economic Comparison of Preventive DC-Side Decoupling and DC Circuit Breakers in Multiterminal Offshore HVDC Grids

The content in this deliverable is based on the following papers:

- M.Van Deyck, G. Bastianel, G. Chaffey, H. Ergun and D. Van Hertem, “Techno-Economic Comparison of Preventive DC-Side Decoupling and DC Circuit Breakers in Multiterminal Offshore HVDC Grids,” in: IET Conference Proceedings CP918, 2025, <https://doi.org/10.1049/icp.2025.1196>. [17]

4.1 Preventive Decoupling Strategy

This section presents an overview of the preventive decoupling protection strategy from [83]. The main principles are explained and the key benefits and challenges, as identified in [83], are discussed. Lastly, the main constraint from the techno-economic perspective is highlighted for further discussion.

4.1.1 Protection Strategy Principle

The proposed principle for MTDC grid protection described in [83] serves as an alternative to (partially) selective protection strategies. According to

this method, the HVDC grid is preventively decoupled, creating separate point-to-point links when the grid is operated in high loading conditions. In such conditions, the loss of the entire HVDC grid due to a DC fault would cause a high LoI in the AC grid, which could result in frequency stability problems and emergency load shedding.

The preventive reconfiguration of the HVDC grid reduces the possible LoI caused by a single DC fault by creating a physical separation between different parts of the grid, i.e. the protection zones. Due to this separation, the decoupled network elements can remain operational in case of a fault in a different zone. As a result, this strategy achieves similar fault impacts as the typical partially selective strategy [84].

The options to either decouple the grid symmetrically or asymmetrically are proposed in [83]. Symmetric decoupling entails that the HVDC grid is fully decoupled by opening HSSs on a given *tie-line* on both poles of the grid. In contrast, asymmetric decoupling implies that the tie-line is only disconnected on one pole of a bipolar system while the other pole remains fully interconnected. Asymmetric decoupling is only possible in bipolar grids with a dedicated metallic return (DMR) and does not guarantee a reduction of fault impact in case of pole-to-ground (PG) faults, since it is impossible to foresee if the decoupled or the interconnected pole would be faulted. However, it does allow the mitigation of the impact caused by pole-to-pole (PP) faults, depending on the total grid capacity, while still retaining some power transfer capacity between the decoupled sections of the grid [83].

Generally, PP faults are assumed to cause twice the impact of PG faults if the poles of the HVDC system is balanced. Therefore, when operating an HVDC grid with the preventive decoupling strategy, it is important to consider whether PP faults or only PG faults are taken into account, since this significantly impacts the power limits for which preventive decoupling has to be carried out. Consequently, the preventive decoupling strategy can be evaluated in the context of these two fault types, while two methods for decoupling, i.e. asymmetrical and symmetrical are possible. Assuming that only one decoupling location is considered per grid, this results in four total *control modes* (M1-M4) that can be evaluated in each case study, as presented in Fig. 4.1. Since asymmetrical decoupling has no effect on the worst-case impact of PG faults, control mode M1 is trivial and does not need to be considered.

4.1.2 Benefits and Challenges

As stated in [83], the preventive decoupling strategy offers as the main advantage the ability to reduce DC-side fault impacts without the need for DC-CBs. Instead, the HSSs used for the reconfiguration would be significantly

Figure 4.1: Control modes for the preventive decoupling strategy based on fault type and decoupling mode.

less costly, and would likely be installed anyway, even if DCCBs were implemented in a partially selective strategy [7]. Moreover, since the protection zones are fully decoupled on the DC-side, converter fault-ride-through requirements that apply in the partially selective strategy do not apply in the preventive decoupling strategy, which can be seen as an additional benefit of this protection concept [67].

However, the preventive decoupling strategy also comes with several operational constraints which are addressed in [83]. Firstly, the preventive grid reconfiguration can only occur if there is no current flowing through the HSSs. This means that a grid-level control scheme is required for controlling this current to near-zero when required. Secondly, since bipolar HVDC grids with DMR are usually low-impedance grounded in only one substation [85], a full symmetrical decoupling of the HVDC grid (including the decoupling of the DMR) would require the grounding to be reconfigured afterwards to ensure a low-impedance ground in each decoupled grid section. A decoupling sequence for both asymmetrical decoupling (i.e. only decoupling one pole) and symmetrical decoupling (i.e. decoupling both poles and the DMR) is presented and validated with EMT simulations in [83]. It is addressed that the implemented decoupling sequence is sensitive to disturbances, e.g. from transient wind power variations, but that this can be mitigated by improving the control method for bringing the current through the HSS to zero, e.g. by implementing a feedback loop.

Lastly, the main drawback of the preventive decoupling strategy is the reduction of power transfer capacity which may result in sub-optimal operating points from an OPF perspective. By removing some or all power transfer capacity between the different protection zones, the key benefit of multi-terminal HVDC interconnection, i.e. improved operational flexibility, is removed. Therefore, the effect of this constraint on the total socio-economic welfare, provided by the HVDC grid should be thoroughly evaluated. In [83], this limitation is addressed and the need for detailed techno-economic eval-

uation is highlighted. However, for the presented four terminal HVDC grid used as an example in [83], which has a total capacity of 4 GW, it is assumed that the socio-economic impact would be low since the decoupling would only take place when the grid is nearly fully loaded (above 75%) and the expected use of the disconnected line would be low.

4.1.3 Proposed Techno-economic Evaluation

This chapter aims to evaluate the impact on the socio-economic welfare, represented by total electrical generation costs, of the preventive decoupling protection strategy versus the partially selective strategy using DCCBs. Since the grid reconfiguration changes the possible paths for power flows in the HVDC grid, the *optimal* flow of power to different market zones may be different for a coupled and a decoupled system. Therefore, the techno-economic comparison is performed by calculating the generator set points and power flows through AC and DC lines using OPF simulations. For this analysis, the power flows in the HVDC grid are mainly of interest. Consequently, AC grids can be represented as single generator models and the flow of reactive power can be ignored, allowing the use of the “DC” linearized OPF formulation for hybrid AC/DC grids [86]. This formulation is computationally less expensive than the “AC” formulation and is commonly used for cost-benefit analyses [37].

Note that only the constant generation costs related to the normal steady-state operation of the power system are used in the computation of the total system costs and that the protection system is assumed to work as expected. This entails that no inherent cost is assumed for the actual decoupling of the HVDC grid and that the required control methods are present to achieve this decoupling, as well as maximally adhering to optimal power flow set points. In addition, since the analysis focuses on the economic trade-offs related to the steady-state operating points of the HVDC grids, fault occurrences are not considered in this study. Therefore, studies on the transient phenomena taking place after faults must still be conducted to fully analyze both strategies from a transient perspective and would be required before implementing either protection concept. In the considered cases, however, the preventive decoupling strategy is inherently designed to mitigate the impact of faults to a similar degree as the partially selective strategy. Consequently, for the proposed techno-economic evaluation, it suffices to quantify the amount of energy not transferred due to the grid reconfiguration, which is carried out preventively in high-loading conditions, regardless of the occurrence of a DC fault.

4.2 Methodology

In order to evaluate the difference in socio-economic welfare between HVDC grids using the preventive decoupling and partially selective protection strategies, both concepts have to be modeled in the OPF framework.

For the partially selective strategy, very few considerations related to the protection system are required in the context of steady-state OPF simulations. The presence of a DCCB in the grid, which is likely to be accompanied by an additional fault current limiting reactor, would cause some additional steady-state losses compared to the topology without these elements. These losses are assumed to be negligible in the context of the current techno-economic comparative study [87]. As a result, the considered systems using the partially selective strategy are modeled as standard multiterminal grids without additional considerations in the performed OPF simulations.

In the preventive decoupling strategy, parts of the grid are decoupled when the total power on the HVDC grid exceeds a certain limit. The power flow set points that determine whether this limit is exceeded are also determined through OPF simulations. Therefore, the implementation of the preventive decoupling strategy occurs in three stages:

1. The standard “DC”-OPF without additional constraints, which is also used for the partially selective case, is used as a perfect forecast of generator set points and the power flows across the grid.
2. In time steps where the results of the forecasting simulation show that the total power in the HVDC grid exceeds the established limits, the tie-line between the considered protection zones is preventively opened.
3. The simulation is run using the decoupled grid model.

This modeling method for the preventive decoupling strategy assumes full advance knowledge of when the power flow conditions would require grid reconfiguration. To correspond with the structure of day-ahead market clearing, the simulations use a one-hour time step. This means that, when required, the grid is reconfigured once per hour. Finally, it is assumed that the reconfiguration happens instantaneously and without costs, transients, or losses that impact the economic evaluation between each hour.

A balanced grid model that represents the full system with a single conductor is used for most simulations. However, since the asymmetrical decoupling principle is inherently unbalanced, a multi-conductor model is required to represent this. Therefore, when asymmetrical decoupling is applied, the HVDC grid model is duplicated with the total capacity halved over each pole and the tie-line removed only on one pole.

4.3 Test Case Description

Two hypothetical HVDC grid test cases of different sizes are considered in this chapter. In the following subsections, the main HVDC grid aspects, i.e. grid layout and protection configuration, are introduced for both test cases, as well as the input data used in the OPF models. Moreover, the constraints for the preventive decoupling strategy can be determined based on the considered grid capacities and LoI limitations inspired by real-world AC grid codes.

4.3.1 Case 1: Four-terminal Grid

4.3.1.1 Topology and location

The first grid case, shown in Fig. 4.2, resembles the four terminal network for which the preventive decoupling strategy is developed in [83]. Two offshore converters, C_1 and C_2 , with nearby offshore wind farms (OWF) are considered. The offshore converters are interconnected with an HVDC tie-line L_3 that either includes a DCCB or an HSS for the decoupling implementation. By placing the protection elements on this line, the grid can be split into two point-to-point links that remain in operation if the other link is lost. Two AC grids are connected via the HVDC interconnectors L_1 and L_2 .

Figure 4.2: Grid case 1: four terminal HVDC grid.

In order to evaluate this grid topology with realistic, publicly available data, the offshore wind farms are assumed to be located in the Baltic Sea near Denmark and the HVDC lines are assumed to connect to the AC grids of mainland Denmark (DKW1) and Germany (DE00) [88], represented in the model by AC_1 and AC_2 respectively. Since these AC grids are both part of the

Continental European Synchronous area, they share a combined maximum LoI limit of 3 GW [39]. An AC connection, AC_{12} , is used in the OPF model to represent the interconnections between these two synchronous grids. However AC_1 and AC_2 are still considered as separate grids in the simulations since they function as separate market zones that can independently influence the power flow set points in the HVDC grid.

4.3.1.2 Configuration and capacity

A bipolar configuration with DMR is assumed for the test case. The power ratings for HVDC lines and converters, offshore wind farms, and AC interconnector are listed in Tab. 4.1. A standard 2 GW capacity per cable and converter station is used for this case, corresponding to the grid ratings presented in [83].

Table 4.1: Power ratings of components in test case 1.

Component	Rated power [GW]
C_1, C_2, C_3, C_4	2.0
L_1, L_2, L_3	2.0
AC_{12}	1.0

4.3.1.3 Input data

The RES and load time series, and installed generation capacities in the AC grids, used for the OPF simulations, are taken from the ENTSO-e Transparency Platform Ten-Year Network Development Plan (TYNDP) [88, 89]. To account for uncertainty in future onshore grids, which will continue developing as HVDC grids are implemented over the coming years and decades, two RES scenarios from the TYNDP are considered. These scenarios represent low and high RES integration pathways in the onshore grids. The increase in installed RES capacity in the high scenario is expected to lower the impact of decoupling in the HVDC grid, as the impact of possible offshore wind curtailment is likely to be reduced. The installed capacities for both scenarios, used in grid test case 1, are shown in Tab. 4.2.

4.3.1.4 Preventive decoupling requirements

Based on the assumptions on the grid topology, and the ratings of components in the test case, the exact requirements for the operation of the preventive decoupling strategy can be determined, as well as the control modes from Fig. 4.1 that are relevant to consider. In [83] this four terminal topology

Table 4.2: Installed RES capacities in test case 1 for the low and high RES scenarios for 2040 from the ENTSO-e TYNDP [88].

Network	Capacity low RES scenario [GW]	Capacity high RES scenario [GW]
AC ₁	18.622	158.561
AC ₂	594.998	942.748
OWF ₁	1.800	1.800
OWF ₂	1.800	1.800

is evaluated only for PP faults using both asymmetrical and symmetrical decoupling, i.e. control modes M3 and M4. These modes are also considered here since, due to the relatively low total capacity of the HVDC grid, no PG fault can exceed the dimensioning incident limit of 3 GW in this case.

In the considered control modes, the following constraints apply for the preventive decoupling strategy:

- M3: asymmetrical decoupling if $P_{C_1,t} + P_{C_2,t} > 3$ GW
- M4: symmetrical decoupling if $P_{C_1,t} + P_{C_2,t} > 3$ GW

$P_{C_1,t}$ and $P_{C_2,t}$ are defined as the power flowing through converters C_1 and C_2 in time step t of the simulation.

4.3.2 Case 2: Five-terminal Grid

4.3.2.1 Topology and location

For relatively small HVDC grids, the economic drawbacks to the preventive decoupling strategy are expected to be relatively limited [83]. Therefore, a larger, five terminal HVDC grid topology is considered in grid case 2. In this hypothetical system, two offshore wind farms are considered in the North Sea. OWF₁ is considered to be located between Belgium (AC₁) and the UK (AC₂) and OWF₂ close to Denmark (AC₃). Besides the five terminal HVDC grid, the considered grid test case includes a parallel HVDC connection (L_6) between OWF₂ and AC₃, and an AC connection AC_{11} between OWF₁ and AC₁.

Since AC₁ and AC₃ represent the onshore AC grids of Belgium (BE00) and mainland Denmark (DKW1) respectively, they are both part of the European synchronous area, similar to the AC grids in grid case 1. However, no AC interconnection between these market zones is modeled in this case, due to the large distance between these systems. Nevertheless, they are still considered as part of the same synchronous AC grid in the context of setting the LoI constraints.

2024, scenario DE2040 [88, 89]. A low and high scenario for RES development are considered following the estimates published in the ENTSO-e TYNDP [88], as shown in Tab. 4.4.

Table 4.4: Installed RES capacities in test case 2 for low and high RES scenarios for 2040 from the ENTSO-e TYNDP [88].

Network	Capacity low scenario [GW]	Capacity high scenario [GW]
AC ₁	30.086	48.81
AC ₂	143.319	174.429
AC ₃	18.623	158.561
OWF ₁	3.500	3.500
OWF ₂	3.400	3.400

4.3.2.4 Preventive decoupling requirements

The system considered in case 2 represents a relatively large MTDC grid connected (directly or indirectly) to the Continental European Synchronous Area at three converter stations, C_2 , C_4 and C_7 , of which two converter stations connect to the same AC grid, AC₁. It should be noted that, though C_7 provides the actual connection to AC₃, the power flow through C_5 must be considered for the preventive decoupling constraints. This is because DC protection strategies, including the preventive decoupling strategy, can only influence the protection zones within one MTDC grid since AC breakers for fault interruption are always expected on the AC terminals of converters. However, even though the power flow through C_5 does not necessarily equal the power through C_7 due to possible infeed from OWF₂, it can be assumed that any power going through C_5 in the direction of OWF₂ is further transferred to the AC grid, since no loads are expected in the offshore wind farm. Consequently, when defining the power limits for the preventive decoupling strategies based on AC grid dimensioning incidents, the power flows through C_5 can be used to quantify how much power is injected into AC₃ from the MTDC grid.

Two dimensioning incident limits are considered for test case 2: i) AC₁ and AC₃ together have a LoI limit of 3 GW, corresponding to the dimensioning incident of the Continental European Synchronous Area [39], and ii) AC₁ is assumed to have a dimensioning incident limit of 1 GW by itself, corresponding to the power rating of the largest synchronous generator in the Belgian system [90]. In the performed studies, the 3 GW limit is only considered for the PP fault cases, i.e. operational modes M3 and M4. This is because it is not possible, in the considered grid layout, to transfer more than 3 GW into the European system on one pole, meaning that no PG fault could exceed this limit. In contrast, for the 1 GW limit, it is not relevant to consider

PP faults in the protection design because, regardless of the selected protection strategy, such faults could lead to an unacceptable LoI if either L_1 or L_3 is loaded above 50% in the considered grid case.

Using these dimensioning incident limits, all three relevant control modes from Figure 4.1 could be considered. However, mode M3 is left for future study here, since the asymmetrical modeling of this grid, along with the decoupling constraints becomes, increasingly complex. This results in the consideration of control modes M2 and M4 for this test case. The decoupling constraints can be summarized for each mode as:

- M2: symmetrical decoupling if $P_{C_2,t} + P_{C_4,t} > 2 \text{ GW}$
- M4: symmetrical decoupling if $P_{C_2,t} + P_{C_4,t} + P_{C_5,t} > 3 \text{ GW}$

$P_{C_2,t}$, $P_{C_4,t}$ and $P_{C_5,t}$ are defined as the power flowing through converters C_2 , C_4 and C_5 . For control mode M2, the limit is taken as 2 GW since, assuming symmetrical power flow, this means that more than 1 GW is injected into AC₁ per pole.

4.4 Results

This section presents the results of the techno-economic comparison between partially selective protection and preventive decoupling for both considered grid test cases. The impact of decoupling the HVDC grid when the established power infeed limits are exceeded can be quantified by the total energy not transferred through the decoupled link, compared to the optimal solution without decoupling. Consequently, as the power flow set points are forced to deviate from the optimal solution, an increase in the objective function, which in this case represents the generation costs in all considered AC grids, is observed. On account of possible inaccuracies in publicly available data and modeling simplifications for the AC grids, only the relative increase in generation costs is presented and no exact cost figures are given.

Besides these parameters relating to the operational cost, it is also relevant to consider for how long the grid is operated in a decoupled way and how many switching actions must occur on a yearly basis. If the system is decoupled for most of the time, system developers might be urged to assess the benefit of implementing a tie-line in the first place. In addition, although no switching cost is considered in this study for the coupling and decoupling of the system, it is expected that, from an operational and component lifetime perspective, it is beneficial to minimize the total number of switching actions.

4.4.1 Case 1: Four-terminal Grid

The four terminal HVDC grid considered in case 1 is reconfigured asymmetrically or symmetrically if the total power being injected from the offshore wind farms is more than 3 GW. In the considered scenarios, this occurs for 231 hours (2.64% of the year) in the low RES scenario, and for 60 hours (0.69% of the year) in the high RES scenario. The lower number of decoupling hours in the high scenario can be explained by the modeled increase in RES in the AC grids, which may cause more energy from the considered offshore wind farms to be curtailed when the total RES availability is high.

For both RES scenarios, it is found that the grid is most commonly decoupled only for short continuous periods, as illustrated by Fig. 4.4. In total, 106 decoupling actions are required in the low scenario while 29 decoupling actions must take place in the high scenario, leading to an average duration of the decoupled operation of 2.18 hours and 2.07 hours respectively.

Figure 4.4: Occurrence rate of decoupling durations for case 1

4.4.1.1 M3: asymmetrical decoupling

The relatively low number of hours for which the grid must be decoupled, combined with the continued availability of part of L_3 in the asymmetrical decoupling mode, results in a negligible amount of energy not transferred through L_3 and a minimal total generation cost increase in the considered scenarios. Therefore, for this specific test case, the preventive decoupling strategy causes no steady-state economic drawbacks, in the considered scenarios.

4.4.1.2 M4: symmetrical decoupling

If symmetrical decoupling is applied, L_3 becomes completely unavailable in the hours when the infeed limit is exceeded. This prevents the transfer through this line of 85.283 GWh in the low scenario and 19.067 GWh in the high scenario, as displayed in Fig. 4.5. These amounts of *energy not transferred* (ENT) make up 3.34% and 0.75% of the total energy transferred through L_3 throughout the year.

Figure 4.5: Cumulative ENT through L_3 due to symmetrical decoupling in grid case 1.

The total unavailability of this line due to decoupling leads to a yearly generation cost increase in the considered AC systems of 0.0057% and 0.0026% in the low and high scenarios respectively.

4.4.2 Case 2: Five-terminal Grid

4.4.2.1 M2: PG faults

For grid case 2 considering PG faults, the grid is decoupled by opening L_5 if the total power through C_3 and C_4 exceeds 2 GW, meaning that there is a risk for PG faults to cause a LoI of more than 1 GW in AC_1 . This results in L_5 being unavailable for a total of 3398 hours (45.64% of the time) in the low scenario, and for 3316 hours (37.85% of the time) in the high scenario. Though the grid is decoupled for a significant portion of the year in both scenarios, the duration of decoupling remains limited in most cases, as shown in Fig. 4.6. A total of 903 and 997 decoupling actions are required, resulting in an average decoupled operation duration of 4.43 hours and 3.33 hours in the low and high scenarios respectively.

Figure 4.6: Occurrence rate of decoupling durations for case 2, considering PG faults.

The decoupling leads to an ENT through L_5 of 648 GWh (12.41%) in the low scenario and 683 GWh (22.50%) in the high scenario. Fig. 4.7 shows the accumulation of ENT throughout the year. The observed relative yearly generation cost increase amounts to $6 \cdot 10^{-4}\%$ and $7 \cdot 10^{-5}\%$ in the low and high scenarios respectively, as summarized in Tab. 4.5.

Table 4.5: Effect of opening L_5 when the cumulative power through C_2 and C_4 is above 2 GW for case 2.

Case 2 scenario	Energy not transferred through L_5 [GWh]	Relative generation cost increase [%]	Number of switching actions [-]
Low	648	$6 \cdot 10^{-4}$	903
High	683	$7 \cdot 10^{-5}$	997

4.4.2.2 M4: PP faults

In the final considered case, symmetrical preventive decoupling is applied if the power through C_2 , C_4 and C_5 exceeds 3 GW, which happens for only 17 hours in the low scenario (0.19% of the time) and 22 hours in the high scenario (0.25% of the time). Similar to the previous cases, the decoupled operation usually has a limited continuous duration with, in this case, an average decoupled operation duration of 1.0625 hours resulting in 16 decoupling actions in the low scenario, and an average duration of 1.5714 hours and 14 decoupling actions in the high scenario, as illustrated by Fig. 4.8.

Figure 4.7: Cumulative ENT through L_5 due to symmetrically the grid, considering PG faults.

The total ENT through L_5 , shown in Fig. 4.9, reaches 26.66 GWh (0.51%) and 37.89 GWh (1.25%) for the low and high scenarios respectively. Due to the very low number of decoupling hours and the subsequent low amount of ENT, no generation cost increase is observed for this scenario. The results are summarized in Tab. 4.6.

Table 4.6: Effect of opening L_5 when the cumulative power through C_2 , C_4 and C_5 is above 3 GW for case 2.

Case 2 scenario	Energy not transferred through L_5 [GWh]	Relative generation cost increase [%]	Number of switching actions [-]
Low	26.66	0.0	16
High	37.89	0.0	14

4.5 Conclusion

The results from the performed comparison between partially selective protection and preventive decoupling in two offshore MTDC grids show that the loss of flexibility caused by the preventive decoupling leads to a small relative increase in the total generation costs in the connected AC grids on a yearly basis. There is a clear difference between the applicability of this strategy depending on the requirements used for preventive decoupling and the size and topology of the considered HVDC grid. For the considered four terminal grid (case 1), decoupled operation is only required for a limited number of hours, which leads to a relatively low amount of energy not transmitted and a low relative generation cost increase, which is even negligible if

Figure 4.8: Occurrence rate of decoupling durations for case 2, considering PP faults.

asymmetric decoupling is applied. In contrast, the application of the preventive decoupling strategy in case 2, when considering the 1 GW loss-of-infeed limit into AC grid 1 for pole-to-ground faults, leads to significantly more periods of decoupling, causing larger volumes of energy to not be transmitted in an optimal way. Despite this, the relative generation cost increase in this case is lower compared to case 1, as a result of the HVDC grid layout and market conditions in the connected AC grids. Using the 3 GW limit in case 2, the grid is decoupled for a very low number of hours, which leads to a negligible relative cost increase. This is also a result of the considered topology and market conditions, which very rarely lead to power flows that require preventive decoupling.

Though the increase in generation costs caused by the preventive decoupling seems limited when expressed relative to the total calculated generation costs - less than 0.01% for case 1 and below 0.001% in case 2 - grid developers can evaluate the trade-off between partially selective protection and preventive decoupling by comparing the cost for a DCCB over its full lifetime with this yearly increase in operational cost. However, it should be noted that additional studies are still required to fully evaluate the preventive decoupling strategy from other perspectives e.g. on the transient fault impact when the grid is not decoupled, the switching cost for decoupling, or the control feasibility for asymmetrical decoupling. Consequently, this chapter presents part of the possible trade-off between protection strategies with DCCBs and the preventive decoupling strategy.

Since no publicly available data on DCCB costs is available, and simpli-

Figure 4.9: Cumulative ENT through L_5 due to symmetrically decoupling, considering PP faults.

fied models were used in the OPF simulations, the results presented in this study can not serve as a definitive basis for selecting either strategy in future systems. However, the performed analysis using indicative figures aims to advance the understanding on alternative HVDC protection concepts, like the preventive decoupling strategy, which can serve as an additional option to the traditional protection strategies in future multiterminal HVDC grid designs.

4. TECHNO-ECONOMIC COMPARISON OF PREVENTIVE DC-SIDE DECOUPLING AND DC CIRCUIT BREAKERS IN MULTITERMINAL OFFSHORE HVDC GRIDS

Chapter 5

Conclusion

In its entirety, this report considers the challenges and opportunities for protection system design in EEHs. It evaluates and builds on existing design options, and proposes methods for the detailed evaluation and identification of the most effective protection system options. The definition, functionalities and challenges proposed in Chapter 2 provide a framework for future research to further consider HVDC protection in the context of electrical energy hubs. The shortlisting method provided in Chapter 3 highlights a key advantage of EEHs for flexible and effective protection system design and offers an applicable method for cost-effective implementation of HVDC circuit breakers in future systems. An alternative protection method without DCCBs is evaluated in Chapter 4 using optimal power flow calculations. Although the analyzed case studies in this chapter are not fully representative of industrial systems, this chapter offers key insights into less obvious DC protection methods and the analysis methodology can be applied on industrial data to arrive at clear conclusions on the applicability of this concept in future EEHs.

5. CONCLUSION

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